

checkCIF/PLATON report

Structure factors have been supplied for datablock(s) op-8-35-red

THIS REPORT IS FOR GUIDANCE ONLY. IF USED AS PART OF A REVIEW PROCEDURE FOR PUBLICATION, IT SHOULD NOT REPLACE THE EXPERTISE OF AN EXPERIENCED CRYSTALLOGRAPHIC REFEREE.

No syntax errors found. CIF dictionary Interpreting this report

Datablock: op-8-35-red

Bond precision:	C-C = 0.0092 A	Wavelength=0.71073	
Cell:	a=19.1336(4)	b=10.5861(3)	c=46.5572(12)
	alpha=90	beta=90	gamma=90
Temperature:	140 K		
	Calculated	Reported	
Volume	9430.2(4)	9430.2(4)	
Space group	P c a 21	P c a 21	
Hall group	P 2c -2ac	P 2c -2ac	
Moiety formula	C54 H34 B2 Co N6 O6, 2(C H2 Cl2)	C54 H34 B2 Co N6 O6, 2(C H2 Cl2)	
Sum formula	C56 H38 B2 Cl4 Co N6 O6	C56 H38 B2 Cl4 Co N6 O6	
Mr	1113.27	1113.27	
Dx,g cm-3	1.568	1.568	
Z	8	8	
Mu (mm-1)	0.655	0.655	
F000	4552.0	4552.0	
F000'	4561.11		
h,k,lmax	26,14,64	25,13,64	
Nref	26268[13290]	23042	
Tmin,Tmax	0.938,0.966	0.870,1.000	
Tmin'	0.788		

Correction method= # Reported T Limits: Tmin=0.870 Tmax=1.000
AbsCorr = GAUSSIAN

Data completeness= 1.73/0.88 Theta(max)= 29.490

R(reflections)= 0.0593(17309) wR2(reflections)= 0.1336(23042)

S = 1.057 Npar= 1352

The following ALERTS were generated. Each ALERT has the format

test-name_ALERT_alert-type_alert-level.

Click on the hyperlinks for more details of the test.

Alert level B

PLAT910_ALERT_3_B Missing # of FCF Reflection(s) Below Theta(Min).

17 Note

Author Response: This is likely due to beam-stop. By using Mo radiation and the geometry of our goniometer, this happens quite often.

Alert level C

STRVA01_ALERT_4_C Flack test results are ambiguous.

From the CIF: `_refine_ls_abs_structure_Flack` 0.460

From the CIF: `_refine_ls_abs_structure_Flack_su` 0.020

PLAT341_ALERT_3_C	Low Bond Precision on C-C Bonds			0.00916	Ang.
PLAT410_ALERT_2_C	Short Intra H...H Contact H6	..H9	.	1.90	Ang.
		x,y,z =	1_555	Check	
PLAT410_ALERT_2_C	Short Intra H...H Contact H20	..H23	.	1.95	Ang.
		x,y,z =	1_555	Check	
PLAT410_ALERT_2_C	Short Intra H...H Contact H34	..H37	.	1.93	Ang.
		x,y,z =	1_555	Check	
PLAT410_ALERT_2_C	Short Intra H...H Contact H60	..H63	.	1.96	Ang.
		x,y,z =	1_555	Check	
PLAT410_ALERT_2_C	Short Intra H...H Contact H74	..H77	.	1.98	Ang.
		x,y,z =	1_555	Check	
PLAT410_ALERT_2_C	Short Intra H...H Contact H88	..H91	.	1.91	Ang.
		x,y,z =	1_555	Check	
PLAT911_ALERT_3_C	Missing FCF Refl Between Thmin & STh/L=	0.600		7	Report

Alert level G

PLAT083_ALERT_2_G	SHELXL Second Parameter in WGHT	Unusually Large		8.81	Why ?
PLAT187_ALERT_4_G	The CIF-Embedded .res File Contains RIGU Records			1	Report
PLAT333_ALERT_2_G	Large Aver C6-Ring C-C Dist C1	-C14	.	1.46	Ang.
PLAT333_ALERT_2_G	Large Aver C6-Ring C-C Dist C29	-C42	.	1.45	Ang.
PLAT333_ALERT_2_G	Large Aver C6-Ring C-C Dist C69	-C82	.	1.45	Ang.
PLAT333_ALERT_2_G	Large Aver C6-Ring C-C Dist C83	-C96	.	1.46	Ang.
PLAT794_ALERT_5_G	Tentative Bond Valency for Co1	(III)	.	3.32	Info
PLAT794_ALERT_5_G	Tentative Bond Valency for Co2	(III)	.	3.37	Info
PLAT860_ALERT_3_G	Number of Least-Squares Restraints			1379	Note
PLAT870_ALERT_4_G	ALERTS Related to Twinning Effects Suppressed ..			!	Info
PLAT912_ALERT_4_G	Missing # of FCF Reflections Above STh/L=	0.600		907	Note
PLAT933_ALERT_2_G	Number of OMIT Records in Embedded .res File ...			11	Note

0 **ALERT level A** = Most likely a serious problem - resolve or explain
1 **ALERT level B** = A potentially serious problem, consider carefully
9 **ALERT level C** = Check. Ensure it is not caused by an omission or oversight
12 **ALERT level G** = General information/check it is not something unexpected

0 ALERT type 1 CIF construction/syntax error, inconsistent or missing data
12 ALERT type 2 Indicator that the structure model may be wrong or deficient
4 ALERT type 3 Indicator that the structure quality may be low
4 ALERT type 4 Improvement, methodology, query or suggestion
2 ALERT type 5 Informative message, check

It is advisable to attempt to resolve as many as possible of the alerts in all categories. Often the minor alerts point to easily fixed oversights, errors and omissions in your CIF or refinement strategy, so attention to these fine details can be worthwhile. In order to resolve some of the more serious problems it may be necessary to carry out additional measurements or structure refinements. However, the purpose of your study may justify the reported deviations and the more serious of these should normally be commented upon in the discussion or experimental section of a paper or in the "special_details" fields of the CIF. checkCIF was carefully designed to identify outliers and unusual parameters, but every test has its limitations and alerts that are not important in a particular case may appear. Conversely, the absence of alerts does not guarantee there are no aspects of the results needing attention. It is up to the individual to critically assess their own results and, if necessary, seek expert advice.

Publication of your CIF in IUCr journals

A basic structural check has been run on your CIF. These basic checks will be run on all CIFs submitted for publication in IUCr journals (*Acta Crystallographica*, *Journal of Applied Crystallography*, *Journal of Synchrotron Radiation*); however, if you intend to submit to *Acta Crystallographica Section C* or *E* or *IUCrData*, you should make sure that full publication checks are run on the final version of your CIF prior to submission.

Publication of your CIF in other journals

Please refer to the *Notes for Authors* of the relevant journal for any special instructions relating to CIF submission.

PLATON version of 10/08/2020; check.def file version of 06/08/2020

